

Heart Sound Classification: A Deep Learning Framework Integrating STFT, Log Mel Spectrogram, and DBN

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Abstract— The classification of heart sounds is crucial for detecting and diagnosing cardiovascular diseases early. This study explores the application of Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) in automatically classifying heart sounds, utilizing Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and log-mel spectrogram as effective audio feature representations. The short-time Fourier transform (STFT) captures the time-frequency features of heart sounds, while the logarithm of the mel spectrogram highlights features that are relevant for perception. The heart sound database includes five categories, including a normal category and four abnormal categories: Aortic Stenosis, Mitral Regurgitation, Mitral Stenosis, and Mitral Valve Prolapse during systole. We preprocess heart sound recordings by transforming them into STFT and log-mel spectrogram representations. These depictions are used as inputs for the DBN, which undergoes layer-wise training and then fine-tuning using back propagation. Our tests show that utilizing both STFT and log-mel spectrogram together greatly enhances the accuracy of classification. The DBN model proposal achieves a 96% accuracy and a 0.96 F1-score on the test set, surpassing traditional machine learning techniques and offering a reliable tool for clinical applications in analyzing heart sounds. The findings have been evaluated in relation to other techniques. The results of the experiment demonstrate that the new method has made considerable advancements and is superior to the traditional methods in terms of effectiveness.

Keywords—Heart sound classification, Deep Belief Networks (DBNs), Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), Log-mel spectrogram, Cardiovascular diseases, Transfer Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

CARDIOVASCULAR diseases (CVDs) remain one of the main reasons for death worldwide, highlighting the significance of identifying and diagnosing them early on. Information concerning cardiac function and pathology can be obtained through recording heart sounds non-invasively with a stethoscope. However, traditional auscultation depends greatly on the skills of the clinician and can be based on

personal interpretation. The demand for automated heart sound classification systems has been fueled by the need for consistent and reliable analysis.

Recent developments in deep learning have displayed substantial potential in different fields, such as medical signal processing. Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) ([10]-[12]), a form of generative neural network, have shown the ability to acquire hierarchical representations of intricate data. This research investigates using DBNs for categorizing heart sounds[13], employing two different audio features: Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT)[4] and log-mel spectrogram[1]. The short-time Fourier transform offers a thorough analysis of the time-frequency characteristics of heart sounds, whereas the log-mel spectrogram highlights aspects important for human hearing.

In this study, we preprocess heart sounds by transforming them into STFT and log-mel spectrogram representations. The feature representations are then utilized in training a DBN[12], which undergoes pre-training at each layer before being fine-tuned through back propagation. Our method seeks to enhance classification accuracy and robustness by merging the advantages of STFT and log-mel spectrograms[1]. The suggested approach shows substantial enhancements in performance compared to conventional machine learning methods, offering a reliable and effective tool for automated examination of heart sounds.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The capacity to track heart sounds has caused a significant increase in the field of identifying cardiovascular disease in recent times. The field of categorizing various heart sounds and developing automated methods to differentiate heart conditions from acoustic data is expanding. Conventional methods of feature extraction from audio signals involve utilizing signal processing methods such as linear predictive coding (LPC) and the Fast Fourier transform (FFT). In classification tasks, these methods have been combined with machine learning algorithms like support vector machines (SVM) and k-nearest neighbors (k-NN). While these techniques have demonstrated promise, there is a chance that they may not be able to completely grasp the complexity and diversity of noise.

Many research projects and practical uses of deep learning techniques have been conducted when it comes to categorizing heart sounds in audio. Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) have shown strong capabilities in accurately classifying data and extracting features from input data.

Singh and Majumder[22] demonstrated the diagnosis of heart disease using unsegmented Phonocardiograms (PCG). Instead of using conventional techniques like PCG segmentation, the scientists utilized wavelet decomposition, Hilbert transform, homomorphic filtering, and power spectral density (PSD) to analyze the first 5 seconds of PCG recordings. The characteristics were categorized utilizing a k-nearest neighbors (KNN) model. In five sets of data, the KNN classifier had accuracy levels varying from 80.95% to 100%. In general, the approach attained a 90% accuracy rate, 93% sensitivity rate, and 90% specificity rate, showcasing superior efficiency with reduced complexity and time when compared to leading-edge methods.

Yaseen and colleagues [21] concentrated on categorizing heart sound signals using various characteristics. The writers suggest an enhanced method for detecting heart conditions by obtaining Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) and Discrete Wavelets Transform

(DWT) characteristics from the heart sound signal. Machine learning methods like support vector machine (SVM), deep neural network (DNN), and k-nearest neighbour with centroid displacement are employed to categorize the characteristics. The outcomes demonstrate that accuracy in heart disorder diagnosis can be enhanced by combining MFCCs and DWT features, with a maximum accuracy of 97% attained. This approach could lead to detecting cardiac diseases early during regular auscultation checks.

Li et al. [23] introduced a method for categorizing heart sounds utilizing wavelet fractal and twin support vector machine (TWSVM). The heart sound signal is broken down by the algorithm using wavelet transform to obtain features like wavelet decomposition coefficients, energy entropy, and fractal dimension. The heart sound signals are classified into normal or abnormal categories using the TWSVM classifier. The proposed algorithm demonstrates better classification accuracy and faster running time compared to traditional SVM-based methods, according to experimental results.

Springer et al. [24] improved heart sound segmentation by combining logistic regression with a hidden semi-Markov model (HSMM) to correctly detect the first and second heart sounds in noisy PCG recordings. Using logistic regression to estimate emission probabilities and a customized Viterbi algorithm, the technique was evaluated on a vast dataset, obtaining an average F1 score of 95.63%, surpassing the current best performance (86.28%). This method shows better segmentation results, which are essential for precise pathological categorization.

Nilanon et al. [25] concentrate on categorizing regular and irregular phonocardiogram (PCG) recordings by utilizing a convolutional neural network (CNN) for the PhysioNet/CinC Challenge 2016. By dividing the recordings into 5-second intervals and using spectrograms and Mel-frequency cepstrum coefficients as features, the model received a score of 0.813, with 0.735 sensitivity and 0.892 specificity.

Dokur and Ölmez [13] introduced a technique for categorizing heart sounds by utilizing discrete wavelet transform and an incremental self-organizing map (ISOM). Wavelet transform is used to segment heart sound recordings and extract features. A peak-detection system that is able to adjust itself determines the timing of S1-S2 sounds. Feature extraction makes use of the information stored in detail coefficients from five different sub-bands. When it comes to classification, Kohonen's SOM and ISOM are compared, showing that ISOM can classify effectively even in noisy conditions. This method assists healthcare providers by offering precise and unbiased analysis of heart sounds.

Kui et al. [9] introduced a new technique for categorizing heart sounds by utilizing log Mel-frequency spectral coefficients (MFSC) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The heart sound signals are cleaned up with wavelet algorithms, broken down using an enhanced duration-dependent hidden Markov model (DHMM), and MFSC features are collected from the heart cycle. CNNs identify these characteristics and combine their classifications through majority voting to achieve the best outcomes. The accuracy of the two-class and multi-class models was 93.89% and 86.25%, respectively. This technique helps in identifying congenital heart disease by providing precise categorization of heart sound signals and assisting in preventative actions.

Li et al. [20] studied the use of transfer learning with Mel spectrograms for classifying heart sounds. PCG recordings were utilized for identification of murmurs, which are essential in diagnosing congenital heart issues. Mel spectrograms were fed into a pre-trained AlexNet that had its layers adjusted for multilabel classification. The database was divided into training and validation datasets, with oversampling done to balance the classes. Findings from the 2022 PhysioNet Challenge indicated promising prospects for using neural network methods in identifying murmurs. The research highlights the importance of transfer learning in helping diagnose heart disease.

Rizal et al. [5] suggested a technique for categorizing typical heart sounds and murmurs by analyzing characteristics from STFT plots with GLDM. STFT visuals are transformed into pictures, and GLDM attributes are computed for categorization with support vector machines. The STFT 200-100 parameters produce 83% accuracy in experimental results. While not reaching the same heights as earlier studies, this technique still provides opportunities for further investigation, like fine-tuning GLDM parameters or integrating different image analysis methods.

Chen et al. [18] study the application of Mel Spectrum and Log-Mel Spectrum characteristics in categorizing heart-sound signals using convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The research examines the theoretical aspects of these characteristics and how they function. Experimental findings indicate that both types of features are efficient, with Log-Mel Spectrum features showing superior performance in minimizing classification disparities across domains. The research helps in understanding the best input representation for CNN models in heart sound classification.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

The methods and approaches employed during the research for the heart sound categorization research are described in detail in this section.

A. Feature Extraction Techniques

The extraction of features is essential in audio classification as it impacts the quality of data for deep learning models. Efficient methods for extracting features play a key role in enhancing model accuracy through the provision of valuable and top-notch audio signal representations.

1) *Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT)*: The STFT is a method to analyze the frequency content of a signal over short time intervals. The Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) is a commonly used technique for segmenting audio signals into small, overlapping sections and analyzing the frequency composition of each section [15]. This procedure generates a time-frequency display of the audio signal, which is advantageous for studying sudden and constantly changing sounds, like those made by heart.

The Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) of a signal $x[n]$ can be expressed as:

$$X[m, k] = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x[n] w[n-m] e^{-j\frac{2\pi k}{N}n}$$

where:

- $X[m,k]$ is the STFT of the signal $x[n]$ at frame m and frequency bin k .
- N is the frame length.
- $w[n-m]$ is a window function applied to the signal.
- $e^{-j\frac{2\pi k}{N}n}$ is the complex exponential function used to compute the frequency content.

2) Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs):

Another commonly used method for extracting features in audio classification is Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs) [16]. MFCCs make use of a mel-scale filter bank to highlight frequencies that are crucial for human hearing [17], providing a representation of the audio data that is meaningful in terms of perception.

The steps to calculate the MFCCs are as follows:

$$MFCC(i) = \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} \log(S[j]) \cos\left(\frac{\pi i}{M}(j+0.5)\right)$$

where:

- $MFCC(i)$ is the i -th MFCC.
- M is the number of mel bands.
- $S[j]$ is the power spectrum in the j -th mel band.

Log-Mel spectrograms and STFT provide in-depth time-frequency representations of audio signals, showcasing important acoustic characteristics. Using DBNs to analyze these visualizations enables the model to understand and acquire hierarchical patterns present in the data. DBNs, made up of several layers of RBMs, are very good at revealing complex structures in the input characteristics. The DBN can identify local and global patterns in the spectrograms due to its layered structure, making it easier to learn intricate details from audio signals.

DBNs' ability to learn hierarchically is improved by their structure, which integrates unsupervised pre-training and fine-tuning. This method enables the network to effectively understand the inherent patterns of the input characteristics and improve them through supervised learning for classification objectives. By using Log-Mel spectrograms and STFT as

3) *Log Mel spectrograms*: Log Mel spectrograms are created from Mel-scale filter banks and are a successful method for extracting features. These spectrograms highlight important frequencies for the human ear, offering a representation of audio data that is relevant to perception [18].

The Log Mel spectrogram is derived in the following manner:

$$\text{Log Mel}(j) = \log\left(\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} |X[i, j]|^2 \times H[j, i]\right)$$

where:

- $\text{Log Mel}(j)$ is the logarithm of the mel-filtered spectrogram at frequency bin j .
- N is the number of the frequency bins.
- $|X[i, j]|^2$ is the squared magnitude of the STFT.
- $H[j, i]$ is the mel filter bank matrix, which maps frequencies to the mel scale.

B. Integrating Feature Extraction and Deep Learning

Combining Log-Mel spectrograms and Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) with Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) has been successful in different audio classification tasks. Providing DBNs with input features from spectrograms allows them to discover intricate, hierarchical patterns and qualities in audio data, thereby improving classification performance. input features, DBNs can target important frequencies and patterns in sound that match well with how the human auditory system works.

DBNs can effectively model intricate features and patterns in spectrograms by utilizing their layered structure, which systematically abstracts and combines input features. This results in a strong portrayal of the sound information, enhancing the model's effectiveness and precision in categorization assignments. Utilizing feature extraction methods in conjunction with DBNs improves the model's capacity to identify various types of audio data, such as various insect species or other audio events, by capturing subtle and important patterns in the audio signals. Furthermore, by including Log-Mel spectrograms and STFT as input features, DBNs can better concentrate on significant auditory patterns, thus improving their ability to precisely classify different audio data. This synchronization with

the human ear allows the model to identify and distinguish various sound events accurately, resulting in more precise audio categorization results.

In short, the merging of Log-Mel spectrograms, STFT, and DBNs creates a robust structure for audio categorization. Utilizing DBNs' hierarchical and deep learning abilities on these feature-rich spectrograms leads to better performance in recognizing and categorizing intricate audio signals.

C. Challenges and Opportunities

Although deep learning has demonstrated great potential in classifying heart sounds, there are still multiple obstacles to overcome. The challenges encompass the complexity and variability of heart sound signals, the need for extensive, annotated datasets, and the variability in recording conditions. Innovative techniques in data augmentation, transfer learning, and model optimization are required to overcome these challenges.

- 1) *Complexity of Heart Sounds*: The complex, non-stationary signals of heart sounds vary greatly due to normal physiological variations and pathological conditions. Developing reliable models to accurately classify various heart sounds across different patient profiles and clinical settings is difficult due to its inherent complexity.
- 2) *Need for Large Annotated Datasets*: Effectively training deep learning models necessitates extensive annotated datasets that encompass a wide range of heart sound patterns. Nevertheless, obtaining and labeling these extensive datasets is laborious and costly, especially in the medical sector where accurate and specialized annotation is essential for model precision.
- 3) *Variability in Recording Conditions*: Various factors like the type of recording device, its quality, background noise, and stethoscope positioning can influence heart sound recordings. These differences may create disturbances and contradictions in the data, which can present difficulties for models to effectively adapt to various recording settings.

To address these challenges, innovative techniques in data augmentation, transfer learning, and model optimization are essential. Data Augmentation methods like time-stretching, pitch-shifting, and introducing synthetic noise can boost the variety of the training dataset, enhancing the

models' adaptability to different heart sound recordings.

Transfer learning by using pre-trained models from similar tasks and adjusting them with heart sound data, the requirement for extensive annotated datasets can be minimized, leading to enhanced model performance through the utilization of acquired features from various domains.

Model optimization by customizing model structures and hyper-parameters for heart sound data can improve the model's capacity to capture the distinct features of these sounds, resulting in enhanced classification accuracy.

In spite of these difficulties, there exist significant possibilities for progress in medical testing and observing. Automated categorization of heart sounds can offer important information on different cardiac ailments, assisting in the prompt identification and assessment.

D. Dataset

This dataset is a public dataset from <https://github.com/yaseen21khan/Classification-of-Heart-Sound-Signal-Using-Multiple-Features-/tree/master>, consists of 1,000 signal samples in .wav format with a sampling frequency of 8 kHz.

The dataset is divided into five classes, consisting of one normal class (N) and four anomalous classes, Aortic stenosis (AS), Mitral regurgitation (MR), Mitral stenosis (MS), and Mitral valve prolapse (MVP).

TABLE I
DATASET

Class	No. of Samples
AS	200
MR	200
MS	200
MVP	200
N	200
Total	1000

Aortic stenosis (AS) is when the aortic valve is too small, narrow, or stiff. The typical murmur of aortic stenosis is a high-pitched, "diamond-shaped" murmur.

Mitral regurgitation (MR) is when the heart's mitral valve does not close properly, allowing blood to flow back to the heart instead of being pumped out. S1 may be low (or sometimes loud) when auscultating the fetal heart. The murmur increases in volume up to S2. A short rumbling mid-diastolic murmur can be heard due to the torrential mitral outflow after S3.

Mitral stenosis (MS) is when the mitral valve is damaged and cannot fully open. Auscultation of heart sounds will reveal an accentuated S1 early in mitral stenosis and soft S1 in severe mitral stenosis. As pulmonary hypertension develops, the S2 sound will be emphasized. A left ventricular S3 is almost always absent in pure MS.

Mitral valve prolapse (MVP) is the prolapse of the mitral leaflets into the left atrium during systole. MVP is usually benign, but complications include mitral regurgitation, endocarditis, and chordal rupture. Signs include a mid-systolic click and a late systolic murmur if regurgitation is present.

E. Preprocessing

In order to get the audio data ready for feature extraction and model training, several preprocessing steps were carried out. These measures guaranteed the uniformity and excellence of the audio signals while assisting in

the identification of important characteristics for the deep learning model.

Normalization and resampling were carried out in order to make the audio signals uniform. The sound data was loaded and standardized to ensure constant amplitude levels. The original sampling rate of 8 kHz was up sampled to 16 kHz to simplify processing and analysis, and to align with the feature extraction process requirements.

Audio signals were analyzed in terms of time and frequency using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). This method divides the sound information into smaller time segments and analyzes the frequency elements of each segment. A frame length of 320 samples, a frame step of 160 samples, and an FFT length of 320 were utilized to assist in the STFT process.

The STFT findings were then transformed into magnitude spectrograms and later processed into Log Mel spectrograms. This change required the use of a Mel filter bank containing 70 Mel bands to highlight frequencies that are important for human perception. The Log Mel spectrograms offer a detailed portrayal of the audio data, emphasizing frequencies that are perceived by humans and capturing important acoustic features for the model. This enhancement increased the precision and quality of extracting features during the training of the next model.

Fig.1. Process of extracting Log Mel Spectrogram from a sound waveform.

F. Deep Learning Framework

The structure of the DBN consists of several layers of RBMs that are trained one layer at a time before being fine-tuned together. Every RBM in the DBN acts as a foundational element

that is trained to depict the input information at various stages of abstraction, capturing detailed patterns necessary for heart sound categorization.

- 1) *RBM Layers*: The DBN starts with an input layer that gets preprocessed heart sound characteristics, like those obtained from Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) or Log Mel Spectrograms. Every successive level in the DBN is made up of an RBM that converts the initial data into more complex representations. An example would be a DBN created for classifying heart sounds, which could consist of hidden layers with 256, 128, and 64 units. These layers gradually condense the necessary characteristics for precise classification.
- 2) *Training Methodology*: Every RBM is trained beforehand using unsupervised learning. This includes understanding the weights and biases that maximize the chances of reconstructing the visible data from the hidden representations. While in the pre-training phase, every RBM is trained to understand the input data by identifying the core structure and patterns found in heart sounds.

Following pre-training, the DBN undergoes fine-tuning through supervised learning. The weights and biases acquired during pre-training are employed to start the deep network, which is later trained on labeled heart sound data to enhance classification performance.

- 3) *Layer Details*: This first RBM layer records fundamental aspects of heart sounds, including simple patterns and primary frequency elements. It uses its hidden units to process the input, becoming skilled at representing these basic features efficiently.

More advanced subsequent RBM layers detect more abstract and intricate characteristics, like patterns associated with particular heart conditions. Every RBM layer changes the input to a more abstract form, forming a hierarchy of crucial features for accurate heart sound classification.

- 4) *Final Classification Layer*: After the RBMs extract hierarchical features from the heart sound data, the last layer of the DBN is a fully connected (dense) layer. This level combines the characteristics acquired by the RBMs and readies the data for the ultimate classification.

The output layer, following the dense layer, employs a softmax activation function to categorize the heart sounds into predetermined groups. The softmax function transforms the results to probabilities, which enables the network to categorize the input heart sound into one of the potential classes.

- 5) *Regularization and Optimization*: Regularization techniques like dropout can be used to avoid overfitting and enhance the model's generalization ability. A dropout percentage of 0.5 applied to the dense layer, randomly disabling half of the units while training to help the model acquire resilient and applicable characteristics. The Adam optimization technique is customized for heart sound classification to enhance the performance of the DBN.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

The experiments and results used to assess the deep learning framework for classifying heart sounds are shown in this section. The experimental setup, model training, performance metrics, experimental outcomes, and result analysis are all included in this part.

A. Experimental Setup

The objective of the research was to assess how well the suggested deep learning system could categorize heart sounds. In order to fully evaluate how well the model performs on various data divisions, the dataset was split into training, validation, and testing sets in the experimental setup.

Data splitting was carried out by dividing the dataset into 50 batches for training sets, 6 batches for validation sets, and 7 batches for test sets. This split allowed for a thorough assessment of how well the model performed on both familiar (training) and unfamiliar (validation and test) data. By evaluating the model on various data splits, we can enhance the understanding of the model's ability to generalize and its robustness.

Baseline methods were used to compare the performance of the proposed deep learning framework. Various machine learning and deep learning algorithms were experimented with.

TABLE II
ACCURACY OF DIFFERENT BASELINE METHODS.

Baseline methods	Accuracy %
Gaussian Naive Bayes	64.05
Logistic Regression	66.13
Decision Tree	71.57
Random Forest	79.71
KNN	82.57
RNN	86.45
CNN	91.25

These initial methods established a standard for evaluating how well the new deep learning model performs. By comparing the accuracy rates of traditional algorithms with those of the deep learning framework, researchers can more accurately evaluate the effectiveness and potential benefits of the proposed approach compared to current methods.

B. Model Training:

The model was trained using the training data and evaluated using the validation data to make necessary adjustments to hyperparameters. The Adam optimizer and a categorical cross-entropy loss function were used during the training process. The model underwent 5 epochs of training using a batch size of 16, enabling it to enhance its performance through training cycles.

In the training period, the Adam optimizer utilized a standard learning rate. This dynamic optimizer is recognized for its capability to adaptively modify learning rates, facilitating quicker convergence and effective learning during training.

C. Performance Metrics:

The effectiveness and accuracy of classifying heart sounds by the model were evaluated using a range of measures.

1) *Accuracy*: Accuracy evaluates the model's ability to make correct predictions among all samples. It is determined by comparing the number of accurate predictions (including true positives and true negatives) to the total sample size. This measure gives a broad look at how well the model is performing, but it could be skewed by uneven distribution of classes in the dataset.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$$

Where:

TP: True Positives (correctly predicted positive samples)
 TN: True Negatives (correctly predicted negative samples)
 FP: False Positives (incorrectly predicted positive samples)
 FN: False Negatives (incorrectly predicted negative samples)

2) *Precision*: Precision assesses the accuracy of positive predictions made by the model, reflecting the ratio of correctly classified positive samples. It is determined by dividing the number of true positives by the sum of true positives and false positives. High accuracy means the model has minimal false positives and can effectively recognize positive samples.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

3) *Recall*: Recall, also referred to as sensitivity, evaluates how accurately the model identifies positive samples from the actual positive samples. It is determined by dividing the number of true positives by the total of true positives and false negatives. A high recall value shows that the model is successful in identifying a majority of the positive samples.

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

4) *F1-Score*: The F1-Score is a metric that provides a balanced assessment of how well the model performs, computed by taking the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It offers a unified measurement that takes into account both incorrect positive and incorrect negative results. The F1-Score is especially beneficial in situations where the class distribution is uneven, as it equalizes the compromise between precision and recall.

$$F1 - Score = 2 * \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall}$$

Together, these performance metrics offer a thorough evaluation of the model's strengths and weaknesses, enabling researchers to assess its overall accuracy, effectiveness in detecting positive samples, and capacity to reduce false predictions.

D. Experimental Results:

The assessment of the deep learning framework for categorizing heart sounds was done by analyzing its success on different criteria. The experiments evaluated how well the model could accurately classify heart sounds and its ability to generalize.

The test set saw an impressive overall accuracy of 96% from the model. The model's high accuracy in classifying different heart sounds from the dataset shows its strong capability in accurately categorizing most of them.

Moreover, the model achieved a 94% validation accuracy, demonstrating its ability to accurately categorize heart sounds within the validation dataset. This indicates that the model has effectively absorbed information from the training set and performed accurately on the validation set.

The model's test set had a loss of 1.15, while the validation set had a loss of 1.14. The minimal loss values validate the model's high effectiveness in forecasting the accurate categories and its certainty in producing precise predictions.

Epoch 1/5	361s 7s/step - accuracy: 0.3002 - loss: 262.5728 - val_accuracy: 0.7917 - val_loss: 2.1625
Epoch 2/5	327s 7s/step - accuracy: 0.8296 - loss: 1.8070 - val_accuracy: 0.9271 - val_loss: 1.6804
Epoch 3/5	387s 7s/step - accuracy: 0.9297 - loss: 1.5050 - val_accuracy: 0.9375 - val_loss: 1.4287
Epoch 4/5	328s 7s/step - accuracy: 0.9514 - loss: 1.3100 - val_accuracy: 0.9375 - val_loss: 1.2010
Epoch 5/5	329s 7s/step - accuracy: 0.9680 - loss: 1.1563 - val_accuracy: 0.9479 - val_loss: 1.1422

Fig.2. Result of 5 epochs.

Graphs were used to display the outcomes of the experiments, showing how the model performed on various metrics and data partitions. These visualizations offered important information on the model's learning process and performance evaluation.

During a 5-epoch period, graphs depicting accuracy and loss were generated for both the training and validation sets. These visual representations showcased the evolution of the model's accuracy and loss, allowing us to track the model's learning advancements. Examining

the trends in these metrics allowed for an assessment of the model's progress and determining the need for any adjustments to improve its effectiveness.

When assessing the model's performance on both the training and validation datasets, it consistently exhibited similar levels of accuracy and loss. This regularity suggests that the model successfully generalized and maintained consistent performance across different data partitions. Successful learning without overfitting is shown by a steady learning progression.

Fig.3. Model Accuracy Graph for Training and Validation.

Fig.4. Model Loss Graph for Training and Validation.

Fig.5. Confusion Matrix.

TABLE III
CLASSIFICATION REPORT

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.96	1.00	0.98	23
1	0.96	1.00	0.98	22
2	1.00	0.88	0.93	24
3	0.96	0.96	0.96	23
4	0.95	1.00	0.98	20
accuracy			0.96	112
macro avg	0.96	0.97	0.96	112
weighted avg	0.97	0.96	0.96	112

In general, these findings underscore the efficiency and promise of using the deep learning model to classify heart sound. The model's impressive results in different measurements indicate its capacity to generalize effectively and manage a range of heart sound data.

E. Analysis of Result

The findings from the study demonstrate the strengths and weaknesses of the model. The model's strong accuracy and F1-score show how well it can classify, indicating its potential for practical applications.

In addition to these strengths, it is important to take into account some weaknesses as well. Slight variations in precision and error were observed in both the training and validation datasets. This difference could suggest that the model is overfitting to the training data, which may result in reduced performance on unknown

data. It happens when the model captures noise or specific patterns that are only in the training data, instead of capturing broader, more general trends.

Multiple error factors could play a role in these disparities and lead to potential overfitting. The model's capability to effectively generalize across different data distributions might be constrained by the dataset's size. Furthermore, changes in recording settings like background sounds, microphone capabilities, and fluctuations in sound levels can add noise and variations to the data, influencing the model's effectiveness.

While the model has potential in accurately categorizing heart sounds, there is still room for enhancement. Researchers can improve the performance and reliability of the model in real-world situations by fixing these weaknesses and error factors with adjustments, increasing the amount of data, or utilizing sophisticated regularization techniques.

To sum up, the model excels at accurately classifying different heart sounds, but improving its weaknesses will enhance its reliability and robustness for practical use. Enhancing the ability to generalize and reduce overfitting can help the model perform better on varied and unfamiliar datasets.

F. Comparative Analysis

An analysis was performed to compare and assess how well the deep learning model works for classifying heart sounds. We were able to assess the model's strengths and weaknesses by comparing its performance to baseline methods commonly used for audio classification tasks.

Compared to methods like Gaussian Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression[24], Decision Tree, Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)[22], RNN and CNN, our deep learning model showed impressive results in terms of accuracy and loss. Its effectiveness in differentiating and categorizing various heart sounds is demonstrated by its high levels of accuracy in classification, especially in challenging audio tasks.

Fig.6. Comparison of different baseline methods with our deep learning framework.

The main benefit of the deep learning framework is its capability to identify complex patterns from spectrograms. This capability enables the model to recognize intricate and nuanced characteristics in the audio data that could go unnoticed with traditional methods. Therefore, the deep learning model can attain increased accuracy and deliver more dependable classifications compared to traditional methods.

In general, the comparison shows that our deep learning model brings about substantial enhancements in comparison to traditional audio classification methods. Its capacity to comprehend and apply insights from intricate spectrograms sets it apart in terms of efficiency, positioning it as a viable method for categorizing heart sounds.

V. CONCLUSION

This study introduces a heart sound classification deep learning model which utilizes Deep Belief Networks (DBNs) combined with Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) and log-mel spectrogram features. Our approach combines the time-frequency traits from STFT and the perceptually important features from the log-mel spectrogram to attain a classification accuracy of 96% and an F1-score of 0.96. These findings suggest that utilizing a combination of these feature representations results in significantly enhanced classification performance as opposed to conventional machine learning techniques.

The deep learning framework effectively showed how to extract complex patterns from audio data by accurately and precisely identifying noises. The model's effective classification performance was enabled by the use of Log Mel spectrograms as input features, which provided perceptually meaningful representations of the audio data. The suggested DBN model shows strength and effectiveness, providing a hopeful tool for the prompt identification and assessment of heart conditions using automated analysis of heart sounds. Future research should focus on acquiring larger and more diverse datasets in order to enhance the model's robustness and ability to generalize. CDBN and transformers are two additional deep learning architectures that can be explored to enhance classification performance in advance. In order to combat potential overfitting and improve model results, additional exploration of advanced regularization methods may be required.

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